

three-leaf stages killed all weeds, some seedlings emerged after its application. Repeated applications may be needed to achieve complete weed kill.

Preemergence applications of butachlor, thiobencarb, and pendimethalin were superior to postemergence applications.

Under wet seeded conditions, preemergence applications of butachlor and thiobencarb, and propanil

application at the two- and three-leaf stages killed *I. rugosum*. Flooding a few days after treatment increased the effect of the preemergence treatments and, with propanil, prevented further weed seedling emergence. Butachlor and thiobencarb applied at the one- and two-leaf stages were not as effective as under dry seeded conditions. Herbicide uptake by the plant seems to be more

effective under dry seeded conditions because the herbicide is more easily leached down into the root zone.

Butachlor applied at the one- and two-leaf stages did not reduce shoot weight. Thiobencarb applied at the two-leaf stage reduced shoot weight. All plants that survived butachlor and thiobencarb treatments were stunted. □

Weed, management in rainfed rice - lentil crop sequence

R. P. Singh, J. P. Singh, Y. Singh, A. K. Singh, and R. A. Singh, Dryland Research Project, Agronomy Department, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University (BHU), Varanasi 221005, India

Rice - lentil is a widely adopted rainfed crop sequence in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Weed control affects yields.

We conducted a field trial 1985-86 and 1987-88 cropping years. Seven treatments were laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Soil was sandy loam with

19.86% field capacity, 5.18% wilting point, 0.32% organic C, 160 kg available N/ha, 15 kg available P/ha, 166 kg available K/ha, and pH 7.7. EC was 0.104 dS/m at 25 °C, bulk density 1.47 g/cc, and water-holding capacity 33.1%. Akashi rice and Pant 209 lentil were the test varieties.

Table 1. Effect of weed control method on weed dry weight and yield of rice and lentil at B.H.U., Varanasi, India.

Treatment	Rice						Lentil					
	Weed dry weight (g/m ²)		Yield (t/ha)				Weed dry weight (g/m ²)		Yield (t/ha)			
	1985-86	1987-88	Grain		Straw		1985-86	1987-88	Grain		Straw	
			1985-86	1987-88	1985-86	1987-88			1985-86	1987-88	1985-86	1987-88
T1 Sowing of both crops with normal tillage and no weed control in either	403	280	0.4	0.4	2.6	3.5	113	163	0.7	1.0	1.1	1.5
T2 Farmer's method (2 hand weeding in both crops)	253	149	2.1	3.0	3.4	5.4	63	89	1.0	1.3	1.5	1.9
T3 Interculture twice by dryland weeder in both crops	325	241	0.9	1.6	3.0	4.3	82	101	0.8	1.1	1.0	1.6
T4 Interculture as in T3 + intrarow hand weeding each time	262	169	2.8	3.6	4.2	5.5	36	40	1.0	1.4	1.3	1.6
T5 Butachlor at 2.0 kg ai/ha at preemergence in rice and no weeding in lentil	178	140	3.0	2.8	4.0	4.2	112	159	0.7	1.0	1.0	1.2
T6 Butachlor at 2.0 kg ai/ha at preemergence in rice, normal tillage for lentil sowing, and preemergence application of prometryn at 0.75 kg ai/ha in lentil	189	135	3.0	2.9	4.2	4.2	92	90	1.0	1.6	1.4	1.7
T7 Butachlor at 2.0 kg ai/ha at preemergence in rice, paraquat application at 1.0 ai/ha after rice harvest, no tillage for lentil sowing, and prometryn at 0.75 kg ai/ha at preemergence in lentil	116	146	3.0	2.9	4.2	4.2	93	90	1.0	1.7	1.9	2.8
LSD (0.05)	156	99	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.9	21	35	0.2	0.3	0.6	0.8

The rice crop received 861.9 mm total rainfall in 1985-86 and 1,050.1 mm in 1987-88; lentil received 51.8 mm in 1985-86 and 74.1 mm in 1987-88.

Application of butachlor in wet season and prometryn in dry season, with and without paraquat, reduced weed dry weight in rice the most (Table 1). In lentil, interculture with intrarow hand weeding reduced weed dry weight the most.

Highest rice grain and straw yields were with interculture twice plus intrarow hand weeding, followed by hand weeding and chemical control. Highest lentil yield was with preemergence application of butachlor in wet season and prometryn in dry season. Interculture was least effective in both crops.

Table 2. Economics^a of weed control treatments in rice - lentil sequence at BHU, Varanasi, India, 1985-88.

Treatment	Mean yield (t/ha)				Value of produce (\$/ha)	Total cost of land preparation and weed control (\$/ha)	Return to land preparation and weed control (\$/ha)	Benefit to-cost ratio
	Rice		Lentil					
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw				
T1	0.4	3.0	0.8	1.3	406.35	250.00	156.35	0.63
T2	2.6	4.4	1.2	1.7	831.07	367.65	463.42	1.26
T3	1.3	3.7	0.9	1.3	551.72	279.41	272.31	0.97
T4	3.2	4.8	1.2	1.4	927.93	308.82	619.11	2.01
T5	2.9	4.1	0.8	1.1	749.00	280.88	468.12	1.67
T6	3.0	4.2	1.3	1.6	926.41	295.66	630.75	2.13
T7	2.9	4.2	1.3	2.3	940.29	306.29	634.00	2.07

^aPrice of produce: Rice: grain - \$132.35/t, straw - \$14.71/t; lentil: grain - 330.88/t, straw - 21.74/t. Cost of treatments: Land Preparation (1) \$8.82/ha, hand weeding (1) \$29.41/ha, interculture by dryland weeder (1) \$7.35/ha, intrarow hand weeding (1) \$7.35/ha, spraying of herbicide (1) \$4.41/ha, butachlor at \$13.23/kg ai, prometryn at \$13.78/kg ai, and paraquat at \$23.85/kg ai. General cost of cultivation: \$214.72/ha.

On a pooled mean basis, highest net return was with preemergence application of butachlor in rice and prometryn following paraquat in lentil (Table 2). □

Managing other pests

Effect of bund dimensions on rodent infestation in irrigated ricefields

V. K. Sharma and A. M. K. M. Rao, Central Plant Protection Training Institute, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

We surveyed 83 transplanted irrigated ricefields 1987-88 to examine the relationship between rodent infestation and the width and height of bunds. Rodent infestation was measured as the

Correlation between rodent infestation and bund dimensions.^a Hyderabad, India.

Bund variable	Crop stage ^b (r value)				
	Seedling (13)	Tillering (19)	Booting (17)	Flowering (21)	Maturity (13)
Width (W)	0.87**	0.79**	0.82**	0.44*	0.77**
Height (H)	0.83**	0.57	0.78**	0.78**	0.63**
W × H	0.80**	0.63**	0.78**	0.64**	0.61**

^aSignificance at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. ^bNumbers in parentheses indicate sample size.

number of live burrows/ 10 m.

The correlation between rodent infestation and bund width was significant at all stages of the crop growth; that between infestation and

bund height was significant at all stages except tillering (see table) when rodents establish themselves. Bund volume (height × width) and infestation were directly related. □

Farming systems

Rice-based cropping sequences for rainfed conditions in midhills of Uttar Pradesh

V. Prakash, P. Singh, and V. K. Bhatnagar, Vivekananda Parvatiya Krishi Anusandhan Shala, Almora 263601, U.P., India

Spring rice (Mar-Sep) is the predominant upland crop in the midhills

of Uttar Pradesh. Because currently available spring rice varieties have long duration, cropping cereals and legumes in rotation is not feasible. The most popular 2-yr cropping sequence is upland rice (Mar-Sep) - wheat (Oct-May) - finger millet (Jun-Oct) - fallow (Nov-Mar), for a 150% cropping intensity.

After shortduration (110 d Jun-Oct) upland rice variety VL Dhan 163 was released, we evaluated 5 intensive cropping sequences for production and return 1985-86 at the Hawalbagh

experiment farm (1,250 m, 29 °36'N, 79° 40'). The split-plot design had crop sequence as the main plot and organic and inorganic fertilization as subplots, with four replications. Soil was a sandy loam with medium fertility.

Rainfed short-duration rice was direct seeded in the wet season, followed by wheat variety VL 421, barley VLB 1, pea VL Matar 1, lentil VL Masur 1, and rapeseed T9 in the dry season. Rice was sown the first week of Jun, the winter crops were planted the third week of Oct. Organic fertilizer treatment was